

The future starts today, not tomorrow

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I have been reading, with some interest, recent articles from farmers concerning future agricultural support. The topic is something I have lived and breathed for quite some time – either through teaching activities, research projects, provision of advice to Scottish Government officials, or talking to farmer groups and like-minded peers.

It is clear to me that there remains confusion regarding what the long-term Scottish agricultural support model will be. As the end of this prolonged period of promised 'stability and simplicity' starts to come into sight over the horizon, the lack of clarity over our future policy direction is understandably becoming of greater concern across the industry – an industry already hit by a prolonged period of Brexit uncertainty and now 'agflation' driven by Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Without that long term policy clarity, farmers and crofters are stuck in limbo, second guessing if a choice made today will impact on their future support. A commitment to a long-term policy structure is needed, and I hope the expected consultation on the future Scottish support framework later this summer will provide farmers and crofters needed clarity. We will have to wait and see what detail comes out in that consultation.

This period of 'talking' reminds me of the long lead-in times during previous CAP reforms. At least in that process the EU Commission proposals were published early, and horse-trading amongst member states invariably softened the proposals. As I have written previously, the Defra Minister and his officials have a vision for England – one where there is no income support, rather farmers will be supported to improve productivity through grants, or supported to improve biodiversity, landscapes and greenhouse gas emissions. It is a model I seriously hope we don't copy – they are designing things on the hoof, which is already leading to industry resentment and claims it fails to deliver the support the sector needs to produce sustainable, healthy food that meets UK standards.

I suppose in Scotland (and indeed Wales) we are inevitably behind the Defra change curve. That is not a bad thing. I say Scotland is 'inevitably behind the curve' deliberately, as any process that has co-construction between officials and all sectors of industry as well as representatives of environmental NGOs takes time. If that time is well spent it can lead to better outcomes than gung-ho, top-down, zealous, approaches. However, time is passing at an alarming rate with draft primary legislation for a new Agricultural Support Bill due in front of the Scottish Parliament by the end of 2023

They say time flies. Indeed, it certainly has regarding agricultural policy in Scotland! As a reminder, we have been discussing and debating this for 5 years. First we had the Agricultural Champions set up in 2017 to help consider the future strategy for Scottish Agriculture. Next the Scottish Parliament agreed to "establish a stakeholder group involving representatives from producers, consumers and environmental organisations to help government thinking through challenges faced by farmers and crofter and how policies might be adapted to help" and the Farming and Food Production Future Policy

Group (FFPFG) was established in June 2019. Unfortunately, consensus could not be formed by FFPFG members on key elements that meant their vision (belatedly published through FOI) remains on the shelf. The Farmer Led Group's were established in 2020 making recommendations on opportunities for future support designs and they have evolved into the Agriculture Reform Implementation Oversight Board (ARIOB).

Whilst I am involved in various discussions with officials and industry groups, I still cannot hand-on-heart say what future support will look like (and there are some that dislike our suggested model). However, the Scottish Government's vision statement for agriculture published in March does provide some glimpses of the future.

"We will transform how we support farming and food production" means the basis of how you get will change after 2025. The as-yet-undefined 'to what' is vital, as decisions made today could determine the rate of support you receive in the future. *"We will have a support framework that delivers high quality food production, climate mitigation and adaptation, and nature restoration"* means that food production will remain supported in the future helping Scotland *"meet more of our own food needs"*. But there will be greater emphasis on provisioning for biodiversity and reducing climate change impacts.

They *"remain committed to supporting active farming and food production with direct payments"* provides a very strong steer that direct support will not be phased out entirely like our neighbours south of Hardian's wall. But the key point is that there will be *"enhanced conditionality of at least half of all funding for farming and crofting by 2025"* meaning you will be faced with more cross compliance style standards as a minimum – with the possibility of optional higher payments available to those that attain certain standards (e.g., calving intervals, slaughter age, nitrogen fixing crops) or undertake certain activities (e.g., increased field margins, improved hedgerow networks, minimum tillage). Hence, your actions today that focus on the 'standards' can potentially help you attain higher tier support in the future.

It is 100% clear that future support will have greater environmental condition as the Scottish Government *"expect recipients of support to deliver on targeted outcomes for biodiversity gain and low emissions production"* but policy mechanisms will also be in place to *"improve business resilience, efficiency and productivity, including through adoption and deployment of technology and innovation"* (including reducing reliance on agro-chemical inputs – which many are doing this year due to input cost rises).

Many of the priorities in the vision appear to resonate with the conditional approach we have suggested to officials and industry for some whilst. We can deliver more, faster, through evolution of our existing structures rather from starting from scratch. I can see the amount of money available to those not attaining 'higher tier' optional standards reducing in the long term as the Scottish Government transition towards meeting their food, economy, biodiversity and climate targets and switches increasing proportions of the budget into higher tier attainment. These conditions still need to be thrashed out and it is important that farmers and crofters engage in the process and provide feedback and ideas. Remember, not everyone is doing things as well as you are, so when you think that a suggested policy measure is meaningless because you are already doing it – recall that many in the industry may not be. If you are already meeting the policy standard you will hopefully be rewarded for doing so, and you may look to other measures to enhance your support and impact further. I remain hopeful that the future can start today, not tomorrow.